

Investigation into Spatial and Temporal Differences in Carbon Emissions and Driving Factors in the Pearl River Delta

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Summary

[Purpose] This study analyzes 2009-2019 carbon emissions in the PRD, probing spatiotemporal trends and drivers for "dual carbon" goals. **[Methods]** Calculate emissions from four components using IPCC coefficients. Analyze variations with spatial autocorrelation and hot/cold spot indices. Assess influencing factors using the Grey-correlation Coefficient method. **[Results]** Energy consumption dominates carbon emissions. Moran's Index decreases, indicating fewer cold spots. Hot spot areas remain stable, with slight shifts in clustering. Economic importance persists, and technological impact grows with green industry. **[Conclusion]** Despite increased carbon emissions, spatial differences are modest, yet diverse factors vary significantly among cities due to multiple industrial influences.

KEYWORDS: carbon emissions; spatiotemporal differences; driving factors; the PRD

1. Research Background

Cities play a pivotal role as primary contributors to carbon emissions, and their coordinated efforts in driving socioeconomic transformation during urbanization are essential for realizing energy efficiency and achieving China's carbon peaking and neutrality goals (Wang et al., 2022a). Despite occupying only 3% of global land area, cities consume approximately 75% of the world's energy and are responsible for about 80% of global carbon emissions (Feng et al., 2023). As a result, achieving carbon peaking in cities is a critical agenda for climate change mitigation (Wang et al., 2022b). The rapid urbanization pace has led to ecological and environmental challenges, including resource scarcity, environmental degradation, and pollution (Li et al., 2021). The relationship between urbanization and carbon emissions is intricate, demanding urgent attention to coordinate these factors effectively. Research on carbon emissions, including detailed spatiotemporal distribution patterns and identification of influencing factors, is paramount. This research not only aids in promoting regional coordinated development but also provides valuable insights for enhancing the scientific, targeted, and practical aspects of energy-saving and emission reduction policies (Wang et al., 2021).

2. Research Innovation and Methodology

Based on existing research, despite the increasing trend in carbon emissions studies, there is still ample room for expansion in this field. Firstly, in the carbon dioxide emission accounting process, mainstream methods primarily concentrate on energy consumption-related emissions in urban areas, resulting in substantial discrepancies between calculated and actual urban carbon emissions (Zhang et al., 2019). Secondly, current research predominantly focuses on provincial scales, with limited attention to individual cities, and there's a scarcity of regional studies centered on cities (Wang et al., 2021). Thirdly, research on regional carbon emissions has primarily emphasized evaluating efficiency and productivity

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differences, with a relative shortage of studies on spatiotemporal variations and driving factors in regional carbon emissions.

Being one of China's major urban agglomerations, an investigation into the spatiotemporal differentiation and driving factors of carbon emissions in the PRD urban cluster is crucial for understanding spatial distribution, temporal evolution, and driving forces in highly urbanized regions. This study aims to provide a scientific reference for achieving "dual carbon" goals by summarizing experiences. Initially, utilizing economic and social data from the "Guangdong Statistical Yearbook," carbon emissions in four sectors—energy consumption, industrial production processes, solid waste, and wastewater—are calculated for the nine cities. Subsequently, the cumulative carbon emissions from these sectors form the total, and spatial autocorrelation analysis examines spatiotemporal differences. Finally, the study measured the impact of several influencing factors, such as Economic Development, Population Size, and Urbanization Level, etc, on the total carbon emissions. The flow of the study is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 Research Process.

3. Conclusion

Utilizing data from nine PRD cities (2009-2019), this study employed spatial analysis and the grey relational model to scrutinize the spatiotemporal distribution of carbon dioxide during urbanization, assessing the impact of influencing factors.

Results show rising total carbon emissions, reaching 18,689.88 million tons in 2019, with an "eastern dominance and western scar" pattern. Energy-related emissions comprised 63.07% to 91.61%, followed by industrial production (6.14% to 32.23%), and wastewater (0.05% to 0.54%).

Clustering patterns persisted, with high-high in Dongguan and Shenzhen, low-low in Shaoguan and Zhaoqing, and low-high in Guangzhou and Shenzhen. Cold spot areas concentrated in Zhaoqing reduced due to increased carbon emissions. Hot spot areas remained stable, primarily in Guangzhou, Shenzhen, and Dongguan. Grey relational analysis revealed the significant impact of economic development (0.907 to 0.835) and a growing influence of technological factors (0.739 to 0.810).

At the local level, Jiangmen and Zhaoqing showed minor variations (difference range < 0.15), while Guangzhou and Foshan exhibited larger fluctuations (difference range ≈ 0.50) in each carbon emission influencing factor.

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Biographies

Engaged in the field of environmental research, I have explored the complexities of carbon emissions in urban settings. With a focus on spatial analysis and driving factors, my work contributes to understanding environmental dynamics. Beyond research, I'm passionate about sustainable development and the intersection of land urbanization and ecology.